

EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

THE IMPLEMENTATION OF STEM ROBOTIC DEVELOPMENT WITH MOBILE APPLICATION CONTROL TO TRAIN STUDENTS' COLLABORATIVE SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

Background: This paper presents the development and implementation of a transporter robot as part of an international collaborative STEM learning program between Universitas Negeri Surabaya (UNESA) and Kumamoto University. **Objectives:** The project aimed to enhance student engagement and technical competencies by integrating theoretical knowledge with practical application in robotics, wireless communication, and mobile programming. **Methodology:** The collaboration adopted a hybrid model in which students from UNESA focused on designing and assembling the robot's mechanical structure and on-board control system, while students from Kumamoto University developed the mobile application and Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) communication interface to enable real-time wireless control. **Results:** Testing results showed that the student-developed transporter robots successfully completed the designed obstacle course with more than 90% success, demonstrating both the technical feasibility of the system and the effectiveness of the applied STEM learning approach. **Conclusion:** These findings confirm that robotics-based learning can strengthen problem-solving abilities, critical thinking, and multidisciplinary collaboration skills. Furthermore, the project provides a scalable educational model that supports interactive learning and cross-institutional collaboration, offering valuable insights for future STEM education initiatives.

KEY WORDS

STEM, Robot, BLE, Collaborative Learning, Mobile.

INTRODUCTION

Robots have been widely utilized across various sectors, including intelligent transportation in industries, healthcare services, entertainment, and even space exploration. Their advantages in enhancing efficiency, effectiveness, and safety make robotics a continually evolving field. In Indonesia, the adoption of robotics has shown positive growth, not only in terms of quantity but also in terms of its benefits. Robotic technologies have been increasingly integrated into both industrial and educational domains.

The use of educational robotics is evident from national competitions such as the Indonesian Robot Contest (KRI), Indonesian Flying Robot Contest (KRTI), and Indonesian Ship Robot Contest (KKI), organized by the Ministry of Education. These platforms promote innovation and collaboration among students, and signify the growing emphasis on robotics in education. Innovation in STEM education is essential to bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application while fostering student creativity and engagement (Khushk et al., 2023). The integration of advanced technologies such as transporter robots can serve as effective tools in connecting STEM concepts with real-world applications (Aveni et al., 2024). Studies have demonstrated that hands-on, experiential learning approaches enhance the effectiveness of STEM education (Giurgiu et al., 2022). Moreover, technology-based learning media, such as transporter robots, can enhance teacher-student interactions and strengthen conceptual understanding (Chaldi & Mantzanidou, 2021).

Given the increasing demand for skilled professionals in robotics, universities must play a proactive role in preparing competent graduates. The Department of Electrical Engineering at Universitas Negeri Surabaya (UNESA) is committed to achieving this through institutional collaboration. Such collaborations are expected to foster idea exchange, joint discussions, and shared insights in the field of robotics education.

Kumamoto University, as a leading institution in technological innovation, offers a conducive academic environment and modern infrastructure to support robotics-based STEM learning. Its reputation as a center for technological excellence makes it a suitable partner for collaboration in developing innovative teaching strategies in STEM.

To address educational challenges, this collaborative program aims not only to introduce transporter robots as instructional tools but also to provide intensive training for both instructors and students at Kumamoto University. Active student participation

is expected to create a more interactive and practical learning experience (Khushk et al., 2023), thereby enhancing STEM education quality at both Kumamoto University and UNESA.

METHODOLOGY

Research Approach

Study is a collaborative research project between Universitas Negeri Surabaya (UNESA) and Kumamoto University, focusing on the development of an intelligent ping-pong ball collecting robot controlled via a mobile application. The robot is designed as an instructional medium to support Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) education (Varela-Aldás et al., 2020).

A hybrid collaboration approach was employed to ensure optimal participation from both institutions, integrating online and offline activities (Bhuyarkar et al., 2022). The offline sessions, conducted at the host university (UNESA), focused on mechanical design, on-board control hardware development, and integration of drive and retrieval mechanisms. Meanwhile, the partner university (Kumamoto University) concentrated on the development of the mobile application and the implementation of Bluetooth-based communication to enable real-time control of the robot via smartphone.

Stages of Development

The research followed a research and development (R&D) model consisting of the following stages, as shown in Figure 1:

Figure 1: Development Stages.

The research development process begins with problem identification and literature review to analyze challenges in STEM education and existing solutions. Based on this review, an intelligent robot system is designed and adapted to STEM learning principles. The design stage includes both hardware and software aspects, ensuring compatibility with educational applications.

Following the design, learning modules are developed to integrate robotics into STEM education, supported by technical training and intensive

workshops aimed at enhancing participants' skills in designing, utilizing, and implementing the robotic systems. Afterward, students from both UNESA and Kumamoto University collaboratively prototype the robot, applying the knowledge and skills gained during training. The prototypes undergo testing and evaluation to assess both robotic performance and learning effectiveness. Data are collected and analyzed using qualitative descriptive methods, which guide iterative improvements and finalize the proposed STEM-based intelligent robotic learning system.

Participants and Collaboration Research at the Host University

The research activities at Universitas Negeri Surabaya (UNESA) primarily focused on the development of the robotic hardware and its control system. The process included mechanical design, selection of electronic components, and integration of sensors and actuators. The communication between the robot and its mobile application was also developed at UNESA, utilizing Bluetooth-based connectivity to enable remote operation. Students participated directly in the design, assembly, and initial testing of the robot, including scenario-based trials to evaluate its functionality in collecting ping-pong balls. In addition, hands-on workshops and focused group discussions (FGDs) were conducted to train students and obtain feedback from both instructors and participants. These activities aimed to strengthen students' practical skills in robotics and control systems, and to support the integration of STEM learning principles into the curriculum.

Research at the Partner University

Kumamoto University contributed by focusing on the development of the mobile application and the implementation of Bluetooth-based communication for the robotic system developed at UNESA. The research involved designing and building an Android-based interface to control the robot's movement, suction mechanism, and ball storage operation in real time. This mobile application enabled seamless interaction between users and the robot, providing an accessible platform for wireless control and data exchange.

Furthermore, Kumamoto University facilitated the integration of this mobile platform into the overall system and provided online technical training sessions on mobile programming and wireless communication protocols. These activities enriched students' skills in embedded systems and application development, supporting the enhancement of innovative STEM learning methods with an emphasis on interactive, mobile-based robotics control.

On Board System Design

Figure 2: On board System Design.

The robot's onboard system is built to be compact and modular. It uses four AA batteries connected in series to supply enough voltage and current to operate the robot's moving parts and control circuits. The main control component is a microcontroller that includes a Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) receiver, allowing wireless connection to a mobile controller.

For movement, four DC motors are used, offering flexibility in mechanical design based on each student's idea, such as differential drive, skid-steer, or omnidirectional setups. The mechanical structure is intentionally open-ended, prompting students to create unique designs and apply knowledge from mechanical engineering, electronics, and control systems within a STEM context (Mohanavel et al., 2022). The overall system layout, as shown in Figure 4, combines power management, signal processing, and motor control, ensuring dependable operation while keeping the setup easy to understand and use.

Mobile System Design

Figure 3: Mobile System Design.

The mobile control system provides an intuitive interface for real-time robot operation via Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) communication as illustrated in Figure 3. It consists of four functional layers: (1) a user interface (UI) containing directional and functional control buttons, (2) a command processing module that translates UI input into BLE

command packets, (3) the BLE stack leveraging Android's native Generic Attribute Profile (GATT) client for wireless data transmission, and (4) a wireless connection enabling direct communication with the robot's onboard BLE service (Oprea & Mocanu, 2021). This modular architecture ensures reliable connectivity and allows seamless integration of future features such as robot status monitoring and extended control modes.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Result

Figure 4: Student-developed Robots.

The results of the student-developed transporter robots show that more than 90% successfully navigated the obstacles provided during testing in Figure 4. This high success rate demonstrates the effectiveness of the applied STEM learning approach, where students designed, built, and implemented their own methods to solve given technical challenges. The outcome highlights not only the functionality of the robots but also the students' ability to integrate theoretical knowledge into practical applications, reflecting the intended learning objectives of this collaborative project.

Discussion

These findings are in line with prior studies that highlight the importance of robotics in STEM education. As stated by Papadakis et al. (2021), using robotics in educational settings can greatly improve student engagement and help them gain a better understanding of technical subjects through hands-on learning. Likewise, Zhang et al. (2021) found that learning with robotics helps students develop stronger computational thinking abilities and increases their interest in STEM areas.

This view is further reinforced by a meta-analysis carried out by Sapounidis, Tselegkaridis and Stamovlasis (2024), which showed that educational robotics encourages teamwork, creativity, and problem-solving skills, especially when students are involved in building, programming, and testing the robots themselves. These results match those from

the Transporter Robot project, where students created their own solutions for navigating an obstacle course and achieved a success rate higher than 90%.

The Transporter Robot project shows that giving students the chance to design their own solutions—using a mobile app and Bluetooth communication—can greatly improve the effectiveness of STEM learning.

The project connects theory with practice, helping students improve their technical skills while also boosting their ability to think critically and creatively when tackling technology-related problems. The real-world focus of this project makes it a valuable model that can be applied in other educational environments, offering a scalable and meaningful approach to modern STEM education.

CONCLUSION

This paper presented the outcomes of an international collaborative project between Universitas Negeri Surabaya (UNESA) and Kumamoto University focusing on the development of a transporter robot as a STEM-based learning platform. Hybrid collaboration model enabled students from UNESA to design and build the robot's mechanical structure and on-board control system, while students from Kumamoto University developed the mobile application and Bluetooth Low Energy communication interface.

Field testing showed that student-developed transporter robots achieved over 90% success in navigating obstacle courses, indicating both the technical feasibility of the system and the effectiveness of the applied STEM learning approach. The project successfully demonstrated that integrating mobile application-controlled robotics into engineering education can enhance students' technical competencies, problem-solving skills, and understanding of wireless communication and embedded control systems.

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